

DARE UK

DARE UK PHASE 1: FED-NET

Creating the blueprint for a federated network of next generation, cross-council Trusted Research Environments

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1. Executive Summary

Solving complex challenges requires data collected for different purposes and from different sources and geographical locations. However, combining data is challenging. There are public concerns about data security/access. Data governance (the legal and ethical framework for data access) is critical. There are technical challenges when combining data collected in different data languages and building secure computer networks which enable collaborative work but protect privacy.

FED-NET builds on the operational Trusted Research Environments (TREs) offered by PIONEER, the acute care data hub¹. A TRE is a secure database, with complete control over what data is placed in or removed from the system and how it is analysed.

FED-NET tested whether federated analytics could offer a scalable solution to the technical and governance challenges of analysing datasets separated by geography and data language. Federated analytics is where different datasets are stored within separate TREs, and instead of the data moving to one location for analysis, the analytical code is sent to each TRE and the results pooled.

Six work packages were delivered;

1. We built and tested the technical architecture to perform federated analytics between TREs with the same and different underpinning structures
2. We curated a real-world dataset including electronic health record, meteorological, air quality and inflammatory biomarker data for patients with asthma. We built a synthetic dataset of the same parameters. We tested if standardised data models/languages were useful with such a complex dataset.
3. We built a metadata catalogue of the data to enable researchers to understand the type data we held.
4. We performed federated analytics across multiple TREs, testing the accuracy of results when using different federated approaches versus pooling the data.
5. We worked with healthcare organisations from across the UK to understand their requirements for federated analytics. This was co-developed into a report and a working group has been formed for future discussions.
6. We worked with diverse patients and members of the public to understand what they wanted to know about federated analytics. We co-produced a public brochure to explain federated analytics. This is now being trialled in wider public groups.

¹ www.pioneerdatahub.co.uk

2. Background

The UK Government Life Sciences Vision has a strategic goal to test and trial new technologies to address societal challenges. Critical dependencies include harnessing the NHS's unique data ⁽¹⁾. Health inequalities are a major challenge ⁽²⁾. Improving health and well-being requires cross-sector collaboration, provisioned with access to highly granular data which spans all major research councils. However, data collected for different reasons and by different systems rarely interoperate.

The public are receptive to the use of anonymised health data for health research and innovation ^(3, 4). The Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) PIONEER Hub co-developed public recommendations, including transparency, limited data exposure and proximity to the NHS ^(5, 6). Workshops with >400 lay members confirmed support for data access for public good, with data exposure limited to “where necessary” and “NHS proximity” as a gold standard.

This creates challenges;

- Can data of differing modalities and languages be combined using a standardised framework, to make them interoperable, research-ready and discoverable?
- Can data be securely stored by its originating Data Controller, with egress prevented but analysis enabled across data providers (a federated analytics model)?
- Does this model serve the analytical need and provide the public and patient assurances required?

Trusted Research Environments (TREs) and data management are the focus of the Goldacre Review ⁽⁷⁾, the HDR UK Data Standards green paper ⁽⁸⁾ and TRE white paper ⁽⁹⁾. PIONEER's TRE infrastructure operates a “data release” model where, following approval from a public panel and the Data Controller, data are transformed prior to loading to the secure TRE environment. University Hospitals Birmingham NHS Foundation Trust (UHB) (lead organisation) and PIONEER (technical and data infrastructure) have combined data from different electronic health systems across 4 NHS hospitals, including structured, imaging and unstructured data ⁽¹⁰⁻¹²⁾.

FED-NET built on the strong foundations of an established alliance to provide a comprehensive data offering to cross-council researchers and innovators. FED-NET includes UHB, the University of Birmingham (UoB), Nottingham University Hospital NHS Foundation Trust (NUH) and The University of Nottingham (UoN). UHB is a Global Digital Exemplar (GDE) trust and the first acute NHS hospital in the Health Data Research UK alliance. UHB has had an electronic health record (PICS) since 1999. Nottingham University Hospitals NHS Trust (NUH) has partnered with Nervecentre since 2010, working towards HIMSS Level 7. NUH has an open-source pipeline as part of Co-Connect,

converting data to OMOP, supporting standardisation without data egress. UoB and UoN have respiratory medicine expertise and biomarker data, expertise in air pollution and the effects of meteorological exposures on health. FED-NET was built on the tested data and technical infrastructure of the PIONEER HDR UK hub.

This DARE UK (Data and Analytics Research Environments UK) sprint has implemented and tested an innovative, scalable, industry-aligned Trusted Research Environment (TRE) and governance model which facilitates enhanced federated data discovery. FED-NET is a technology demonstrator, which includes establishing best practice for governance and a driver use case. Our initial use case was agreed based on priorities of partner NHS organisations, the ability to demonstrate cross-council utility and following public engagement. FED-NET focussed on a test case of asthma, including clinical, meteorological, pollution and translational data.

Asthma is one of the most common long-term conditions in the world and the UK has amongst the highest prevalence of asthma in the world. Asthma costs the UK public sector over £1.1bn per annum with 100,000 inpatient episodes for asthma and over 1000 asthma deaths each year⁽¹³⁾. Pollution and air quality impact the frequency and severity of asthma exacerbations⁽¹⁴⁾, especially the TH2 asthma immunophenotype⁽¹⁵⁾. Asthma outcomes are worse across the Midlands than other UK regions⁽¹⁶⁾ and there is a planned region-wide effort to focus on asthma outcomes, in line with the grand challenges outlined in the Life Sciences Vision⁽¹⁾.

PIONEER curated granular health data focusing on emergency presentations of asthma, describing patient cohorts, access to specialty services, specialty consultations and any resultant change in immediate management versus additional elective investigations or treatments. Separately, we have date and location matched environmental data and data focusing on inflammatory readouts.

The UKRI councils served by the test case include MRC, EPSRC, InnovateUK and NERC.

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3. Aims & Objectives

Our vision is that the developed infrastructure and governance will scale to serve a broad and vibrant cross-council research portfolio, tackling health inequalities through access to interoperable data reflecting health, the community, translational science and the environment, using a federated analytics approach which has public support through transparent oversight.

Aim for Phase 1: To expand our existing data infrastructure, digital architecture and governance process, to develop and test a federated analytical environment that can combine data from diverse sources into common data models, and assess public trust, using a test case of asthma.

3.1 Objectives:

- Establish federated TRE and analytics functionality –interoperating a federated network across data sources aligned to UKRI research councils (NERC, MRC, InnovateUK, EPSRC for test case).
- Establish Resource Description Framework (RDF) – a standard model for data exchange on the web using application programming interfaces (API)
- Build data visualisation tooling for participating data controllers and researchers.
- Install SPARQL to enable privacy-preserving federated analytics across multiple TRE databases.
- Test the scalability of current governance/ethics through agreed SOPs and contractual templates.
- Ensure continued transparency and public involvement through workshops, with EDI a central priority.
- Expand the metadata catalogue (UHB PIONEER) with more discoverable data assets by constructing a metadata exchange model.
- Adopt and agree on a common data model for the test case.
- Capture data controller and end user feedback (NHS/industry/academic), which will feed into Phase 2.

The test case included linking meteorological, air quality data, inflammatory phenotype with granular data on acute hospital admissions for asthma (2018 – 2020; demography, co-morbidity, severity, treatments, physiology, outcome). This test case provided a vehicle to combine disparate datasets, which is of relevance to both localities.

3.2 DARE UK FED-NET Aims

The FED-NET team set out the following aims for the DARE UK sprint (**Figure 1**):

Figure 1. Diagram listing FED-NET aims for the DARE UK Sprint. All six work package aims across fields of technical, data, governance and public trust have been achieved.

This report will detail how these aims have been met via the DARE UK FED-NET sprint.

4. Work Packages Summary

The programme was divided into the following work packages (WP):

- **WP1:** Build the Technical architecture, including API integration. This provided the foundations for the federated environment.
- **WP2:** Build data infrastructure and common data model. Ensuring standardisation and quality assurance of the cross-council data.
- **WP3:** Metadata – production and process. To enhance discoverability of data assets.
- **WP4:** Federation of analytics and TREs: including the deployed data use case and gaining end-user feedback in discussion groups. Explored industry views on the TRE blueprint and operational processes via our Memorandum of Understanding with the ABPI.
- **WP5:** Governance and ethics. Assessed how the PIONEER governance model can scale over 2 sites. Deployed the template DLA and receive external data controller/end-user feedback in collaboration with DARE UK
- **WP6:** Patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) included reviews of data access throughout DTC, and a series of workshops discussed our approach to TREs.

4.1 FED-NET Sprint work package timelines

Figure 2. FED-NET Key monthly achievement timeline from project kick-off to finalising the final report.

5. Work Packages 1: Technical Architecture

Aims

Build the technical architecture, including API integration. This provided the foundations for the federated environment.

The FED-NET PIONEER architecture (Figure 3) automates the Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) Five Safes framework². It supports a full range of analytics, from basic aggregate summaries and statistical analyses to advanced machine learning (ML). Contemporaneous metadata can be pulled or pushed, via a secure standards-based RESTful Application Programming Interface (API) created and made readily accessible over Hypertext Transfer Protocol HTTP. A RESTful API is a technical interface that allows computer systems to exchange information securely over the internet using HTTP requests.

A central PIONEER metadata gateway implements Message Broker architecture, allowing remote organisations to ‘subscribe’ to real-time events.

Figure 3. FED-NET high level technical architecture diagram. At **stage 1**, data from the NUH and UHB Electronic Patient Record (EPR) has been cleansed (including National Data Opt Out), normalised and sent to the hospital’s own Trusted Research Environment (TRE) in an anonymised form. At **stage 2**, the anonymised data is checked and undergoes QA/QC by the appropriate team from the NHS Hospital sites, e.g. the PIONEER team on the UHB TRE. From this data, a metadata catalogue is formed, providing detailed data descriptions, which describe the data each TRE holds (PIONEER, Nottingham, UHB). This TRE houses technical architecture to ensure sensitive data is held securely. At **stage 3**, the metadata exchange, APIs in the TREs allow the metadata to be exchanged using resource description framework (RDF), an industry standard approach for data models. At **stage 4** the cross-council data such as meteorological, pollution and early phase clinical trial is accessed, and metadata retrieved. At **stage 5**, the PIONEER TRE acts as the message broker for all the metadata (from all

² <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/help/secure-lab/what-is-the-five-safes-framework/> accessed 26.08.2022

cross-council feeds) via the metadata exchange. The final **stage 6** is where researchers (subscribed to the FED-NET metadata service) can review the metadata for their research questions. It is this metadata that enables the production of statistical and analytical queries which are then passed back (via the metadata exchange) to the TRE housing the appropriate data to run the query. Once the query has been run, each TRE data controller has been provided with the rights to review and approve the release of the aggregate analytical output. If approved the results are provided back via the exchange to the researcher in their portal at **stage 6**.

5.1 FED-NET Application Programming Interface

The technical team was tasked with developing a standards-based system to facilitate secure data exchange between the system components, including:

- TREs containing data assets
- The FED-NET Central platform
- Remote Researchers

Solutions were based around existing standards to maximise ‘interoperability’, which is the potential for distinct systems to easily intercommunicate. This was achieved by building a data exchange infrastructure incorporating:

- A data manipulation tool build using the globally popular Microsoft programming framework ‘.net’;
- The Microsoft ‘Azure’ cloud platform to host various components including an exemplar TRE, and the ‘central’ system which assimilates / federates data from various sources
- The ‘Representational State Transfer’ (REST) protocol for moving data from one component to another, taking advantage of data communication protocols most likely to be available in target systems such as TREs
- The ‘Really Simple Syndication’ (RSS) protocol for creating a ‘push’ system allowing Researchers to register their interests with the FED-NET platform, and for the platform to automatically push matching information to them as it arrives in real-time
- The global Microsoft ‘Active Directory’ system, a de-facto international standard, to host *authentication* (who are you?) and *authorisation* (what are you allowed to do?) settings, allowing the components to securely interact

These standards, platforms and components collaborate within a workflow as follows:

1. Store TRE metadata to the FED-NET Central API:

Each TRE contains research data. This data can be described without revealing any sensitive information by means of generating metadata. A goal of the FED-NET system was to assimilate metadata from multiple sources to create a federated information source suitable for analytics.

The first task for the FED-NET platform was to link TREs with the FED-NET Central platform. This was achieved by building and deploying a simple utility into the TRE. This utility can be scheduled to run automatically on a schedule, and has the following tasks:

- Run a query against nominated databases in the TRE to generate metadata
- Convert the metadata into an agreed standard such as ‘RO Crate’
- Securely send this metadata from the TRE into the FED-NET Central platform where it is unpacked, curated, and used for analytics and syndication.

The data receipt into the FED-NET Central platform is achieved by implementing an 'Application Programming Interface' (API). This was developed using the .net framework and C# programming language. This secure API authenticates the sender and receives the metadata in RO Crate format. The standards used for this data exchange include built-in security and quality checks. Once the data is received onto the FED-NET Central platform, it is stored into a database implemented using the popular 'Postgres' product for secure long-term persistence.

2. Retrieve metadata from the FED-NET Central API:

Once metadata is securely stored in the FED-NET Central platform, it becomes available for several use-cases. These include the RSS service, and the Analytics service. The central platform can *receive* data, via its API, and can also *return* data on request to authorised systems using the same REST protocol.

3. Retrieve specific metadata from the FED-NET Central API:

In certain circumstances, a remote system or User may have advance knowledge of specific data they know is stored in the central platform. In this case, the central API can respond to a 'GET' request qualified with a key value, such as the name of an image. This usefully allows the FED-NET platform to be interrogated for catalogued content, and to be able to return specific information when asked.

4. Store Analytics Result File to the FED-NET Central API:

This ability to receive and return different data assets allows the FED-NET central API to act as an information broker, not just for metadata, but for analytics. Metadata is stored within the Postgres database as distinct columns of data, whilst images are stored in the original binary, which is a non-loss solution, maintaining original quality.

5.2 Service Accounts

The FED-NET security model allows for the creation and maintenance of 'accounts'. These entities can be linked to individuals, or to systems. This flexible approach allows for systems to collaborate using secure interoperability standards whilst completely under the control of the FED-NET administrator. FED-NET used the Microsoft Azure Active Directory system to provide a unique service account that was created for each TRE. This unique account enabled Metadata and Analytical results to be posted to the Central API.

5.3 Authentication

In the case of a 'service account', the FED-NET administrator will provide authentication credentials to a remote system wishing to connect, for example to send metadata from a TRE, or to send or receive analytics data.

The authentication solution implements popular open-standard protocols to facilitate friction-free integration, including 'OpenID' and 'OAuth'. These protocols collaborate following industry standard

workflows to generate a 'token' which can be used to securely and efficiently access the FED-NET central API within the minimum of delay.

The token is an agreed representation of the service account credentials held in a very compact form. An example of the FED-NET Microsoft OAuth2 workflow is shown in **Figure 4**. Detailed technical architecture is shown in **Figure 5**.

Figure 4. Microsoft OAuth2 Flow. This diagram shows how a client system (**Browser**) and the target system (FED-NET central API) collaborate using highly secure standard protocols to agree the identity of the client, and to provide an efficient means for the client to access the FED-NET Central API (shown as **Web Server**). The process is initiated with a researcher using their browser to navigate to the FED-NET web application (stored on a Web Server). The Web Application then efficiently redirects the user to Azure Active Directory which is used to validate the user identity. The user is then prompted to enter their login credentials and consent to the permissions from FED-NET. If the username and password are verified the Microsoft Identity platform via OAuth2) (pale blue central line) then an ID token is returned to the user's browser. This ID token is then passed to the FED-NET Web Server using Redirect URI where, if a valid token, the user will have access to a secure page for their session on FED-NET, where they can retrieve analytics or browse metadata.

Figure 5. Detailed FED-NET Technical Architecture -section diagram. In **section 1** shows the components within a distinct TRE which collaborate to extract metadata and send to the central FED-NET federation platform. In **section 2** Central FED-NET federation platform receives metadata from contributing TREs, with the data being securely persisted. **Section 3** demonstrates a federation use-case based on the in-built RSS service. A remote researcher registers a speculative interest in certain cross-council data. The central FED-NET federation platform responds by identifying matching persisted assets, and returns summary information to the researcher’s RSS client, e.g. their Web Browser. **Section 4** details another federation use-case based on the in-built Analytics API. Both the remote researchers are using FED-NET to store and produce analytics.

6. Work Package 2: Data Infrastructure

Aims

Build a data infrastructure and common data model. Ensuring standardisation and quality assurance of the cross-council data.

6.1 Data Acquisition

Real-world clinical data (see **Section 6.2**) were queried from UHB clinical systems using PIONEER’s local data warehouse; weather data from the UK Meteorological Office were retrieved from CEDA, and pollution data downloaded from the UK Department for the Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) website, joined and staged locally before use as a template for the generation of synthetic data (see **Work Package 4**). Figure 6 shows data sources and Table 1 the data headings. Figure 7 shows the process for the data factory for FED-NET.

Figure 6. FED-NET Data sources. Data were obtained from UHB and NUH Hospitals, Nottingham and Birmingham BRCs IL6 Translational data (synthetic), DEFRA pollution data and CEDA Meteorological data.

group	Minimum requirement	Data field description	Notes about data fields
	y	patient pseudonym	
	y	admission pseudo-ID	
parameters on admission	y	month of admission	1-12
		hour of admission	0-23
	y	day type	working day or public holiday/weekend
		Particulate Matters 10 (PM10)	previous 24 hours
		Particulate Matters 2.5 (PM2.5)	previous 24 hours
		Nitrous oxide (NO)	previous 24 hours
		Nitrogen dioxide (NO ₂)	previous 24 hours
		Sulphur dioxide (SO ₂)	previous 24 hours
		air temperature	previous 24 hours
		relative humidity	previous 24 hours
		dew point	previous 24 hours
	patient background	y	asthma type
y		age on admission	Not bucketed
y		Sex	
y		Ethnicity	
y		Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD)	
		height	
		weight	
		Body Mass Index (BMI)	
		smoker	yes/no/previous
		Fractional Exhaled Nitric Oxide (FeNO)	Parts per million (ppm)
		Forced Expiratory Volume (FEV1)	Percent predicted
		Eosinophils	
	Interleukin 6 (IL6)		
presenting state		respiratory rate	
		O2 saturation	pulse oximeter
	y	National Early Warning Score (NEWS2)	
		Immunoglobulin (IgE) test	
	y	oral steroids	yes/no
	y	Inhaled steroid	yes/no
treatment	y	admitted	yes/no
		onward transfer from Acute Medical Unit (AMU)	yes/no
	y	length of stay	in hours
	y	nebulised reliever	
	y	Intra Venous (IV) Magnesium	
	y	Oxygen	
	y	oral steroids	Prescribed in hospital
	y	Inhaled steroid	Prescribed in hospital
		Booked for follow-up	yes/no
O/C	y	Survived	yes/no
	y	Intensive Therapy Unit (ITU) admission	yes/no
		Readmission in following 30 days	yes/no

Table 1. Demographic table for UHB real-world patients alongside the UHB and NUH synthetic data. Data are number (percentage) unless otherwise stated. Ethnicity in the real-world data was self-reported.

Figure 7. FED-NET Data Factory. This diagram shows the process that extracts, loads and transforms FED-NET cross-council data for federated analytics by researchers. The **Extract** process commences with ingress into a secure area (TRE/On-prem server), where there are multiple steps undertaken including two QA/QC checks, data cleansing, applying Opt-Outs (local/National – where appropriate) and anonymisation. The next phase is **Load**, where data is egressed into the appropriate secure area (TRE/On-prem server). There are again numerous steps including a further two QA/QC checks, extraction of metadata, loading of data as a stock for researchers. The final stage for research-ready data for federation is **Transform**, where the data are converted to the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (**OMOP**) Common Data Model (CDM) format. This stage is where the **metadata** along with analytics are **federated** and results staged for **research**. Subject to approval from the relevant Data Controller the aggregate results are **egressed** and shared with the researcher. The FED-NET system **archives** these results to ensure reproducibility (if ever required).

6.2 Real-world data

A demographic summary of the real-world data from UHB alongside the synthetic data is provided (**Table 2**). The majority of the real-world patients were female (67.5%) and white (55.2%). These data were used to create 40,000 synthetic patients’ data (see **Section 6.4** for the synthetic generation methods adopted). Of note, the median age, higher proportion of female and white patients is observed in both UHB and NUH synthetic data.

	Real-world UHB patients n=1767	UHB Synthetic Data n=35000	NUH Synthetic Data n=5000
Age in years: median (IQR)	45 (29 – 62)	38 (22 -56)	38 (22 – 55)
Sex, n (%)			
Female	1193 (67.5)	23177 (66.2)	3325 (66.5)
Male	574 (32.5)	11823 (33.8)	1675 (33.5)
Self-reported ethnicity, n (%)			
White	975 (55.2)	17153 (49.0)	2494 (49.9)
Mixed/ Multiple	51 (2.9)	713 (2.0)	89 (1.8)
Asian/ Asian British	379 (21.4)	11519 (32.9)	1605 (32.1)
Black/ African/ Caribbean/ Black British	102 (5.8)	1229 (3.5)	170 (3.4)
Other ethnic group	58 (3.3)	874 (2.5)	115 (2.3)
Preferred not to say	74 (4.2)	994 (2.8)	159 (3.2)
Not known	128 (7.2)	2518 (7.2)	368 (7.4)

Table 2. Demographic table for UHB real-world patients alongside the UHB and NUH synthetic data. Data are number (percentage) unless otherwise stated. Ethnicity in the real-world data was self-reported.

6.3 Analytical Data Model

All statistical tests and machine learning systems require an array of vectors as input, sometimes referred to as a “flat” dataset. Much has been proposed around the use of common data models (CDMs) such as Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP), but most such models do not constitute the required flat datasets and require further querying to this end before analytical testing can be performed. Furthermore, based on previous experience of PIONEER, flat datasets are extremely simple and unambiguous to specify whilst more complex, generic CDMs can be extremely time consuming to build, and still leave a lot of wrangling needed before analysis can proceed.

Information governance concerns around anonymity can often be allayed in a flat dataset by aggregating or removing certain information, such as providing length of stay, hour of admission and month of year instead of admission and discharge date-times. For this analytical dataset therefore, a flat dataset was specified that could readily be loaded into existing analysis packages without any extensive downstream querying, and that would afford significant levels of anonymity. However, the PIONEER Technical team have extensive experience in wrangling and anonymising complex healthcare datasets as the need arises in future developments.

For further comparison, a heat-map is presented (See Figure 8) showing which fields of the FED-NET test asthma dataset can be held in a popular CDM, OMOP, which can't, and which ones would require further wrangling and calculation in addition to the necessary table joins. There were 43 fields in total that were assessed in the heat-map.

- Green denotes fields that exist as-is and can be transformed to OMOP CDM, these accounted for 51.2% of fields.
- Amber fields require further calculation and may not be obviously supported by OMOP, requiring locally-specific use of certain codes and features. These fields required further calculation from OMOP to extract (admission/readmission, length of stay, ITU visit), or non-obvious approaches to indicate (drugs history, transfer from AMU). The other risk we had to mitigate is the release of identifiable information (admission month, hour and day type, length of stay and re-admission). This was non-trivial and required the experience of the PIONEER team to calculate appropriately. These accounted for 25.6% of fields.
- Red fields cannot be held in OMOP, as there are no defined mapping for these data types and fields. These accounted for 23.3% of fields.

Of note, using OMOP as a basis for this FED-NET dataset required basic wrangling for all fields, for instance to filter down to the first eosinophils reading of a given admission to hospital and to encrypt pseudonyms for deployment into a specific research data asset.

As seen in the OMOP heat-map, approximately a quarter of the cross-council data cannot natively be inserted into the OMOP schema as the CDM was not designed to handle it. Fields that are excluded from OMOP are all those which do not form a regular part of clinical data such as the weather and Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) scores, and also follow-up bookings (highlighted in red). The use of the OMOP CDM will need to be considered for future phases of this FED-NET programme.

Data	OMOP Rating	Notes
patient pseudonym	Green	
admission pseudo-ID	Green	
month of admission	Amber	requires release of potentially identifiable data (admission date/time)
hour of admission	Amber	requires release of potentially identifiable data (admission date/time)
day type	Amber	requires no change to admission date/time - makes potentially identifiable
Particulate Matters 10 (PM10)	Red	
Particulate Matters 2.5 (PM2.5)	Red	
Nitrous oxide (NO)	Red	
Nitrogen dioxide (NO ₂)	Red	
Sulphur dioxide (SO ₂)	Red	
air temperature	Red	
relative humidity	Red	
dew point	Red	
asthma type	Green	
age on admission	Green	
Sex	Green	
Ethnicity	Amber	
Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD)	Red	
height	Green	
weight	Green	
Body Mass Index (BMI)	Green	
smoker	Green	
Fractional Exhaled Nitric Oxide (FeNO)	Green	
Forced Expiratory Volume (FEV1)	Green	
Eosinophils	Green	
Interleukin 6 (IL6)	Green	
respiratory rate	Green	
O ₂ saturation	Green	
National Early Warning Score (NEWS2)	Green	
Immunoglobulin (IgE) test	Green	
oral steroids	Amber	OMOP has no native concept of drugs on arrival
Inhaled steroid	Amber	OMOP has no native concept of drugs on arrival
peak flow	Green	
admitted	Amber	requires calculation (possible for experienced users)
onward transfer from Acute Medical Unit (AMU)	Amber	OMOP has no concept to describe a care site
length of stay	Amber	requires calculation but requires potentially identifiable data (admission and discharge date/time)
nebulised reliever	Green	
Intra Venous (IV) Magnesium	Green	
Oxygen	Green	
Booked for follow-up	Red	
Survived	Green	considered potentially identifiable data
Intensive Therapy Unit (ITU) admission	Amber	requires calculation (possible for experienced users)
Readmission in following 30 days	Amber	requires further disclosure of identifiable information

Figure 8. OMOP Heatmap. Colour-coding of fields from the test Asthma dataset, green denotes fields that exist as-is, amber fields require further calculation and may not be obviously supported by OMOP, requiring locally-specific use of certain codes and features, and red fields cannot be held in OMOP.

One limitation of using an OMOP data source is the need to transform the data tables into a flat analytical data table to undertake the federated analyses. Therefore, the data was extracted from the cross-council sources, transformed into OMOP (where possible) only to be re-transformed into flat tables. For some analyses, it would be potentially beneficial to use the source data format, balanced with the need for common data model formats.

6.4 Synthetic Data Generation

A synthetic asthma dataset was generated first by testing the 4 tabular models available in the SDV library¹⁷. However, these methods resulted in a consistent loss of correlative information as demonstrated with temperature vs. month of year (see Figure 9 and 10)

Figure 9. Monthly atmospheric temperature distributions Observed in template data (red) and synthetic data produced by various algorithms (as noted). Template data is sampled on a per-admission basis (one row per admission) and so some days may be sampled more than once, and some days may not be sampled at all. Data cover the years 2018 and 2019

Figure 10. Monthly atmospheric temperature distributions Observed in template data (red) and synthetic data produced using the TVAE and CT-GAN algorithms. Comparison is with the column on the far-right that contains a post-hoc sampling constraint that will probabilistically reject synthetic data rows based on the temperature distributions inferred from the raw weather data, calculated before joining to the health record data.

The TVAE method produced the range of temperatures most closely resembling the template data but was sensitive to unbalanced counts in the data and tended to synthesise only the dominant values in each column. CT-GAN was selected for further tests.

To correct the temperature correlations, a sampling-rejection constraint was developed by inferring a Gaussian distribution over the range of temperatures for each month of the year using the original weather data, and then synthesised data rows were probabilistically rejected according to this distribution. Whilst the SDV library has the functionality to apply such constraints as defined by the user, it will also attempt to apply them to the template data and would fail due to the probabilistic

nature of this constraint, and so this was applied downstream of the synthetic data sampling by rejecting rows and resampling until the desired number of rows were reached.

This approach was taken with all synthetic datasets, with the added reassurance of clinical datasets being evaluated by clinical experts (in the case of asthma, a Respiratory consultant).

6.5 RO Crates

As part of the evolution of the FED-NET platform, the team have utilised RO-Crates, a community effort to establish a lightweight approach to packaging research data with their metadata, to allow metadata to be packaged for sharing. RO-Crates is based on schema.org annotations in JSON-LD, and aims to make best-practice in formal metadata description accessible and practical for use in a wider variety of situations, from an individual researcher working with a folder of data, to large data-intensive computational research environments. This includes useful information such as the context, provenance, schema, and methods used to create the underlying data. It is a highly effective way of describing data resources for the purposes of efficient information exchange.

One limitation of the RO-Crates model is that the contextual information about the data within a file or database resource is limited. To develop federated analytic queries that can effectively run across multiple data resources the underlying structure of the data, including the field names, the field type (Varchar, Date, Integer etc) and most common values (i.e., sex could be M/F/U) needs to be understood.

A range of tools exist that can index a dataset and generating this underlying information. One of the easiest to implement is [White Rabbit](#), developed by OHDSI to index data resources prior to ETL into the OMOP common data format. The main function of WhiteRabbit is to perform a scan of a data resource to provide detailed information about the internal structure of that resource. White Rabbit has been designed with security in mind. Obfuscation of results (low number suppression) is enabled by default to ensure that no disclosive information about a resource are exported in the scan reports.

The RO-Crates Schema.org model allows for the insertion of property values that can be used to add additional descriptions to a given files metadata. To describe the details of underlying data resources held within SRE environments (in a format that is portable and can be transferred between SREs) we propose a model whereby a sanitised outputs of a White Rabbit scan report is converted to JSON and embedded directly within the RO-Crates JSON_LD propertyvalue field. This allows us to describe the structure of the data resources and the contents of those files in a format that is standardised.

The data is available for the test case. Phase 1 has provided tested TRE and governance blueprints to enable data access and knowledge transfer across UKRI research councils and ICS localities, with

public involvement and engagement. See

'Federated' TREs

- Health economics
- Genomics
- Meteorological data
- Air pollution / particulate matter
- Early phase clinical trials (+ translational endpoints)
- Clinical data

Figure 3 for an overview.

7. Work Package 3: Metadata Production

Aims

Metadata – production and process. To enhance discoverability of data assets.

7.1 RSS Feed

Really Simple Syndication (RSS) is a popular format for packaging and exchanging data between interested parties. It is a standard and protocol commonly used where individuals or systems declare an interest in certain data assets and are proactively informed when they become available. There are many free and paid for 'RSS Reader' software packages available, including those built-in to modern Web Browsers. This solution was chosen for the purpose of linking Researchers with FED-NET data assets.

RSS (RDF Site Summary) is a web feed that allows users and applications to access updates to websites in a standardized, computer-readable format. Subscribing to RSS feeds can allow a user to keep track of many different websites in a single news aggregator, which constantly monitor sites for new content, removing the need for the user to manually check them. News aggregators (or "RSS readers") can be built into a browser, installed on a desktop computer, or installed on a mobile device.

This information is fetched by a user's RSS feed reader that converts the files and the latest updates from websites into an easy-to-read format. An RSS feed takes the headlines, summaries, and update notices, and then links back to articles on your favourite website's page.

This content is distributed in real time, so that the top results on the RSS feed are always the latest published content for a website.

7.2 Functional Requirements

Functional requirements for FED-NET were gathered through a series of workshops with individuals identified as potential system users. Following these sessions, the FED-NET team were able to describe the technical functionality of the system, as described below.

- The data scientist (researcher) should be able to create a RSS News and Information Feed that relates to either a dataset they hold or save a metadata request to run their analysis on. This will include the use of RSS Feed Reader Chrome Extension by Feeder.co which facilitates subscription, feed management and instantaneous notifications when new posts are added.
- The researcher should be able to subscribe to the RSS Feed so that updates can be shown in their web browser feed reader. This feed enables the researcher to know when any new data is updated, or fields added.
- The system should notify the researcher when new metadata is posted in the FED-NET PIONEER Metadata Hub. This enables the researcher to respond promptly or amend their analyses with any new fields added to their 'saved' favourites, or if any metadata has been updated.

- The data scientist should be able to search for feeds for an interested topic, for example the addition of early phase clinical trial data related to asthma patients (as in FED-NET case study).
- Creation of a WEB API using .net framework to enable the posting and returning of feeds to registered users (researchers)

7.3 Non-Functional Requirements

Non-Functional requirements for FED-NET were also gathered through a series of workshops with individuals identified as potential system users. Following these sessions, the FED-NET team were able to describe the required operation of the FED-NET system, as defined below.

- Performance: A new user account shall be created in less than 2000 ms
- Reliability: The system shall have at least 99.9% availability
- Scalability: The system shall be horizontally scalable to increase the number of simultaneous users.
- Usability:
 - Users should be able to navigate to any page in the site within 3 clicks.
 - Information content in the feed should be brief and basic information about the full content.
 - RSS Feed should contain the title, description and link to the website.

7.4 Usage

Data Scientists can use RSS feeds to publish their researched meta datasets and analytics. This RSS feed is an online file that contains details about every content a researcher has published. As RSS feed allows you to create a customized meta dataset of the most up-to-date content for the topic or research that has been published.

This FED-NET application has used the RSS technology to help Data Scientists publish their work to assist with wider dissemination. Researchers can subscribe to these Feeds to be informed of developments in their areas of their interest.

7.5 Implementation

Using .Net 6 , we have created a Web API. We have exposed an endpoint that can return a syndication feed RSS 2.0. This API has used the Microsoft Syndication Feed class which has all the information about a feed. It has created a service that exposes a syndication feed using both Atom 1.0 and RSS 2.0. This service exposes one endpoint that can return either syndication format.

7.6 RSS Feeder

RSS Feeder or aggregator is responsible for the convenience of RSS feeds. A screenshot of the FED-NET RSS Feeder dataset test page is provided below (Figure 11). The RSS aggregator checks websites

for new content automatically. It immediately pulls that content over to the relevant feed reader, thus avoiding manual checking of content.

Figure 11. Screenshot of the FED-NET RSS Feeder data page. This shows a user (Researcher) view where three datasets the researcher subscribed to have been updated. Each dataset has a title and description. This can also include details of what has been updated in the dataset.

The aggregator keeps track of what you have and have not read by listing the number of articles or pieces of content for each website you are following that has not been seen. The Data Scientist creates an RSS feed that maintains a list of new updates or notifications. These approaches have been applied to publishing alerts and now can be applied to metadata updates and outputs arising from data use.

8. Work Package 4: Federated Analytics

Aims

Federation of analytics and TREs: including the deployed data use case and gaining end-user feedback in discussion groups. Explored industry views on the TRE blueprint and operational processes via our Memorandum of Understanding with the ABPI.

Much of the work on federated analytics has focussed on the ML/AI space. However, the Artificial Intelligence Index Report 2021³ has highlighted that only 3.8% of all peer-reviewed scientific publications worldwide included AI in 2019. Considering this, FED-NET focused on whether federated analytics would support traditional statistical methodologies.

We examined two different modes of federation; first by simulating a federated environment and then moving on to federation using the FED-NET API.

8.1 Data Split

We modelled two ways that data may be split between federated environments – split by rows, or split by columns, as illustrated in the figures 12 and 13 below. Here, the orange and navy cells show the split in the data, and the grey titles denote data common to all federated environments.

row ID	independent 1	independent 2	outcome

Figure 12. Data split by Row. Row split data, wherein all environments in the federation (coloured in orange and navy) hold data with the same set of columns for every row ID

³ <https://aiindex.stanford.edu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/2021-AI-Index-Report-Chapter-1.pdf>

row ID	independent 1	independent 2	outcome

Figure 13. Data split by Column. Column-split data, where each environment, coloured in orange and navy holds different fields for a common row_id, coloured in grey.

Most existing datasets should be immediately compatible with row-split data, and the modes discussed in the next section assume it. Column split data requires reconfiguration of the libraries or even a ground-up implementation to ensure interoperability. In this latter case, a neural network trained using back-propagation would need to have its input nodes split between the relevant environments, and weights updated locally during training based on information broadcast out of the main host environment about node weights in the next layer. Decision trees would require signals to be sent out of which ever TRE hosts the data on which a split is evaluated during training, to inform the other environments which row IDs belong to which branch.

Classical statistical methods are usually provided through a single function call to which data are passed. Whilst these methods are compatible with column- or row-split data, the functions provided in existing packages would need extensive modification to work such as decomposing into multiple smaller functions so that the results of intermediate calculations from aggregate, federated data can be provided in lieu of the raw data. Parametric tests are commonly based upon the mean, standard deviation and covariance, all of which can be safely federated, extracting aggregate data from their respective environments.

With row-split data both the numerator and the denominator of the global mean are local aggregate statistics that can be safely exported from a TRE, and can be added together in order to compute the global mean for a given column. In column-split data, only one environment hosts each column, so the global mean can be computed locally and exported for each column hosted in each environment (**Equation 1**).

$$global\ mean = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

Equation 1. Global mean of column x , computed as the sum of all values of X across all TREs in the federated environment, divided by the total row count across all TREs (N)

Standard deviation (**Equation 2**) in the row-split data needs the global mean to be imported into each environment, and the summed portion can then be computed locally before exporting back out of the environment and added together in the central hub. Again, this is far simpler for column-split data where each column is hosted in its entirety in its respective environment, and can thus easily be computed locally for export.

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$$

Equation 2. Standard deviation over column x which can be computed once the global mean, \bar{x} , and the total row count in all TREs (N) is known, so that the summed residual of all x per row i can be computed locally and exported as aggregate data

For covariance (**Equation 3**), row split data is the easiest to deal with since all columns are hosted locally in each environment, and so the numerator and denominator can both be computed for export. In column-split data however this becomes more complex, requiring the following two steps:

1. For each row, the environment hosting the x component computes the vector [row id, (x_i - \bar{x})] for each row id. This data is now aggregated, but cannot be exported to the central hub, since the central hub will know the value of \bar{x} and so can compute every value of x_i
2. This data is thus sent to the environment hosting the y component, which can then compute (y_i - \bar{y}) for each row id, join this to the x component data on row id and send the summed product back to the central hub.

$$cov_{x,y} = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{N - 1}$$

Equation 3. Covariance between two columns x and y, here again relying on the prior federated calculation of the global means over each column, \bar{x} and \bar{y} , and the total row count, N.

8.2 Federated Learning

For the federation of machine learning, there exist, depending on the methods chosen, two different modes of federation when data are split row-wise:

1. “Online” learning where a single model is initialised and then passed between all federated environments, learning as it goes before being returned to the central hub once all the data in all environments has been exhausted.

2. “Concurrent” learning, where separate models are trained in each federated environment and returned to the central hub where they are combined or averaged in some way

These are summarised in Figure 14.

Figure 14. FED-NET Federated Analysis System blueprint. This demonstrates two modes of federated learning and the traditional pooling mode where all data are extracted from each federated environment and pooled in a central location. The federated learning system passes an AI model into each environment which can then be updated (online learning) or fully trained (concurrent learning) using compute resources local to each environment, without exposing data outside of its respective environment.

Ensemble methods such as Random Forests lend themselves to the concurrent mode of federation, since they are natively comprised of multiple smaller models and can be trained independently and then pooled to generate the final model. We tested these modes using synthetic data in a simulated environment, before progressing on to testing on the same data in a federation of UHB and NUH systems, using the same synthetic data.

Whilst for extremely large and complex models this may significantly slow the training process, for the majority of applications on structured data this slowdown is unlikely to affect the workflows used.

Prior testing of federated learning was conducted using the Python programming platform by generating 3 simulated TREs and populating them with data generated by the CT-GAN synthetic data generation model using unbalanced counts of rows, with 1K, 2K and 5K rows per TRE. The federated learning was tested using Gradient Boosted decision trees, with the Catboost18 python interface. Catboost was selected for its native support for categorical variables. Catboost natively supports the two learning modes using the following functions:

1. Online learning – each separate environment can specify the `init_model` parameter to Catboost’s `fit()` method, which each `init_model` being the model trained in the previous environment, or the model as initialised before training
2. Concurrent learning – models trained in each environment can be combined using the `sum_models()` method

	concurrent	online	pooled	template		readmitted?
precision	0.17	0.16	0.16	0.17	yes	
recall	0.44	0.47	0.39	0.50		
<i>F</i> - β score ($\beta = 1$)	0.24	0.24	0.23	0.25		
precision	0.86	0.85	0.85	0.89	no	
recall	0.61	0.56	0.64	0.63		
<i>F</i> - β score ($\beta = 1$)	0.71	0.68	0.73	0.74		

Table 3. describes the comparison of precision/recall values for a model trained to predict whether a patient would be readmitted within the 30days following discharge, for various modes of machine learning using Catboost, also including metrics for a model trained on the template data. The training/test split was 9:1 for the concurrent, online and pooled methods, and 4:1 for the template data as the row counts for the template data were much lower than for the synthetic data.

Precision values seemed comparable across the methods tested (**Table 3**) whilst recall values seem somewhat more variable. Further optimisation may be possible by weighting the contribution from each environment based on the number of rows in an environment relative to all other environments, for instance in the online mode, the number of training epochs might be scaled proportionally, or with concurrent mode, the number of ensemble units (trees in this case) might be scaled likewise.

FED-NET’s file API endpoint was utilised to execute a training cycle using the concurrent mode of federation, using as client environments an instance of PIONEER’s TRE and a local machine at Nottingham University. The FED-NET team needed to pivot to a local machine test at Nottingham due to delays experienced in Governance and Technical issues. Model files were approximately 2MB in size each and so presented no issues in terms of load times when using the API, and both were successfully combined as in the test environment.

8.3 Federated Analytics

To test federation of a simple one-way ANOVA, we used the file POST endpoints from the API to ship the aggregate components to the central FED-NET hub, using PIONEER’s TRE and a local computer hosted at Nottingham University as the sources. The null hypothesis under test was the distribution of sulphur dioxide levels in the atmosphere in the 24 hours prior to emergency admission to hospital following an asthma attack are the same for patients that were and were not re-admitted to hospital within 30 days of discharge from their initial admission.

The aggregate data exported from each environment were:

- Row count (number of valid rows that did not contain null values)
- Sum of all (non-null) sulphur dioxide readings
- Sum-squares within each group (re-admitted, not re-admitted)

Manual computation of P-values was performed using the same analysis performed automatically on the pooled data from both environments in Microsoft Excel. Mean Squares and associated P-Values were the same for both the federated and pooled data ($P < 0.01$). That both modes produced the same result illustrates the possibilities of federated statistical analytics such as this, either standalone or in support of AI development.

8.3 Discussion

Whilst at the technical level, federation of both machine learning and more classical statistical tests is perfectly feasible; the governance issues surrounding it present a larger problem. Operating based on presumptive authorisation for immediate export of arbitrary results from a TRE may be infeasible, and Data Controllers would undoubtedly wish to authorise export of all results.

However, a system wherein the nature of the exported data is known a-priori may be more amenable to presumptive authorisation, as long as row count is known to be greater than 1 (i.e. degrees of freedom are greater than zero), aggregate data that supports classical statistics might be acceptable for pre-authorisation of export when implemented using a single, known API, which would speed the completion of results and drawing of conclusions greatly when compared to the need to manually authorise each export.

8.3 Future work

To fully implement a federated analytical system across multiple trusted research environments necessitates the provision of number of components:

1. For federated learning, a Secure Aggregation Protocol (SAP) layer so that the central hub can securely update a global model using updates provided only as a weighted average over multiple/all TREs, without ever revealing to the central hub the contribution from each individual TRE, thus preventing certain attacks against the model such as model inversion, or data exfiltration by updating the model with exactly 1 row of data at a time. Compatibility of this layer with existing AI/ML platforms would be ideal
2. Secure TRE to TRE communication support to enable analysis of column-split data (see above on covariance calculations), as well as secret sharing for the SAP layer

This must also consider the recommendations of other DARE UK hubs which may include modifications to existing algorithms or constraints over certain hyper-parameters of the models, to maintain full anonymity in any resulting AI models.

For classical statistical tests, a dedicated API endpoint with pre-implemented tests would be most likely to satisfy ethical, governance and IP concerns as each test will thus be a known entity to all data controllers, and so stands the greatest chance of being accepted based on presumed authorisation, rather than having to manually authorise each aggregate exfiltration from each TRE. Any constraints on these methods, such as always having more than 0 degrees of freedom, would

need to be considered a-priori. Dedicated analytical endpoints will also require local implementation in each TRE to provide the data to the endpoints, yet the only constraints it is possible to guarantee will apply to data flowing into such an endpoint is that the aggregate data must be of the correct data type (e.g. numerical, text, etc), there is no way for the central hub to verify the analytical correctness of the data it receives. This means that the API can be tested very simply by sending it random numbers for instance; however an exemplar implementation of a local TRE provider would be highly desirable, as has begun with this project in the PIONEER testing TRE (see previous work packages), and it may be appropriate to define acceptance tests or some form of certification to ensure that correct results are sent to the central API from local providers.

9. Work Package 5: Governance & Ethics

Aims

Assess how the PIONEER governance model can scale over 2 sites. Deployed the template DLA and receive external data controller/end-user feedback.

9.1 Data access agreements status & confirmation of governance arrangements

PIONEER provides a robust framework for milestone delivery, accountability, governance & task ownership, IP management, contract requirements and compliance, with SOPs and template Data Licence Agreements (DLA) already seen by all partners. UHB have sought external legal advice to produce a template DLA for use across healthcare, commercial or academic organisations seeking to access data for research and innovation. Of note, data sharing infrastructure, an agreed standardised data model, a governance model and patient/public oversight is already established at UHB through PIONEER, with published use cases, providing strong foundations which the proposed work will utilise and expand upon.

This programme built on PIONEER's robust governance framework, including reporting lines via:

- Executive Group: featuring representatives of all active data providers
- Management Group: with an emphasis on outputs, risk management, and budget control
- Digital Platform Group: to design, build and integrate the TRE and federated data platform
- Public Data Trust Committee: reviewing data access requests and assessing public interest versus perceived risk.

9.2 Ethics and data: governance approval

FED-NET builds on the existing and proven governance process in place; developed as part of our HDR UK Hub, PIONEER. This successful model has been operational at UHB for 24 months with 64 data applications supported from academic, commercial, government & NHS researchers, with data access provided to >250 analysts. PIONEER provides licensed access to health data. PIONEER has an approved Privacy Impact Assessment from UHB alongside Health Research Authority (HRA:20/EM/0158) & Section 251 (20/CAG/0084) approvals to link and provide data for research.

These overarching approvals ensure consistent, ethical, data and information governance processes across providers, while increasing our agility in servicing data requests. Despite curating data from multiple sources, PIONEER operates with a single data controller (UHB). This ethical and governance framework has been used for FED-NET, but now using a joint data controller model with NUH, so each data controller retains control of its own data. Of note, UHB has experience in joint data controller, through the INSIGHT Hub (UHB and Moorfields).

UHB data is stored on a secure, UHB-controlled Microsoft Azure cloud platform in accordance with the fourteen UK Cyber Cloud Principles, which include data protection in transit; asset protection and resilience; separation between users; a robust governance framework; operational security;

secure user management; identity and authentication; and audit. The cloud provision has been externally audited and accredited with the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 27001 standards, an international specification for information security management. The UHB database platform complies with the Department of Health Information Governance policies and standards for secure processing of patient healthcare data, as set out in the Information Governance Toolkit of the Health & Social Care Information Centre. The database platform has undergone cybersecurity checks by an independent and external company (QinetiQ). The platform's design enables the rapid build of bespoke Trusted Research Environments (TREs) which provide approved & licensed researchers with access to specific curated, de-identified datasets and a suite of analytical tools. PIONEER is committed to promoting the protection of privacy & data security in line with the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Recommendation of the Council on Health Data Governance. A data flow diagram for FED-NET Phase 1 is provided in **Figure .**

Data Access. All requests for licensed data access are reviewed against the principles of the 'Five Safes' by the Data Trust Committee (DTC) and UHB as Data Controller. The DTC are a diverse, lay committee who review all data requests & determine whether data access is in the public good. The group is recruited through open application and members range in age from 19 to 75 with over 40% BAME representation, as well as members who self-define themselves as living with a long-term health condition, having physical and mental disabilities, a carer of a person with complex health needs and a member of the LGBTQ+ community. 80% of quorate membership must approve data access before data access is agreed (pending legal contracts) and a decision not to support data access by the DTC is binding for PIONEER. If this threshold for support is not met, data access is not provided, so the DTC decision is binding and final.

During the last 12 months, the DTC has expanded, changing to two groups meeting every two weeks, with increased feedback from data requestors as to how interactions with the DTC improved their project. These changes followed the DTC reviewing their processes and impacts.

PIONEER reserves the right to refuse an application, or limit the data fields available, based on the view of the DTC and any concerns around possible identification. The 'Five Safes' framework includes an assessment of the safety of the project, safety of the researchers requesting access to the data, safety of the data (the risk of disclosure or re-identification) and safety of the data setting. PIONEER has contractual safeguards, with data access licensed to expressly preclude any attempts at re-identification & limit the use of the data to the purposes described within the contract, within a specific time frame. The final "Safe" refers to safe outputs, ensuring the statistical results of data analysis are non-disclosive.

Within FED-NET, we have identified and prepared the needed datasets and considered and agreed that the PIONEER process will be used to manage ethical, legal and governance issues relevant to the project (such as data protection, research approvals and meeting information governance standards), with responsibilities clearly established.

Figure 15 provides an overview of the steps from a researcher browsing our Metadata Gateway through to the application process and highlights the key ethical, governance and legal steps to ensure adherence to national and local policies. There are also notes provided how this existing PIONEER process can be scaled as the programme expands.

Figure 15. An overview of PIONEER FED-NET data flow processes.

Scalability of the PIONEER FED-NET data flow processes.

The PIONEER system and the recently developed FED-NET infrastructure have been designed to ensure they are scalable. The scalability is achieved as follows:

- PIONEER FED-NET Gateway and infrastructure can support multiple researchers and searches in concurrent sessions.
- The Data Request Form (DRF) can be iterated, but it is worth noting that the existing PIONEER template has enabled the processing of >64 requests. The current template ensures all the relevant information is provided to adhere to the Five Safes, Due Diligence, Governance, Legal and Lay Summary.
- The teams are currently set up to be scalable with automated processes, and this will enable further automation and expansion as required.
- The Data Trust Committee (DTC) for PIONEER was expanded recently to include more diverse members and representation. Furthermore, we created groups to allow us to meet the increased demand so we aren't putting unnecessary pressure

on the Committee. The plan will be to further expand via recruitment to include representation from Nottinghamshire (East Midlands area).

- Contract – UHB have recently worked with an external legal firm to revise the Data Sharing Agreement (DSA) to ensure the contract covers all the requirements for Data Controllers. This has enabled the legal process to operate more efficiently.

9.3 End Users Governance Workshop

FED-NET wished to understand the views of key decision-makers in the health data research space regarding data discovery, access and federated analytics.

To capture these views, the FED-NET programme held workshops for strategic data providers and end-users to explore their views on the health data / research landscape, their current awareness of TREs, the perceived benefits and challenges of running a TRE, and the expectations and uncertainties of federated analytics and future data analytics tools.

The final FED-NET workshop was held virtually on the 30th June 2022. After brief presentations on the current landscape of health data research and federated analytics, there was an open discussion between our attendees, who included Chief Information Officers (CIO), Chief Clinical Information Officers (CCIO), TRE Leads, Informatics Programme Managers, Data Scientists and Data Architects, representing NHS and academic organisations and the charitable sector. The attendees from NHS Trusts included representation from across the home nations. There was also representation from the university sector, national charities, and health research regulators.

Several themes emerged through the group discussion. These were expertise, resources and sustainability; equity of provision and access; public trust; harmonisation of standards and approach; scale; and interoperability.

9.3.1 Expertise, Resources and Sustainability

The benefits of providing access to unconsented health data were acknowledged and all present wished to provide access to data, governance allowing. However, there were concerns about risks and varying levels of experience in this field (from none to highly experienced). Some organisations felt they lacked the expertise to engage with TREs at all or provide access to health data at scale. CIO/ CCIOs reported that NHS organisations faced a challenge to find the resources required to build or deploy electronic health systems, curate data for research and build and run TREs. Resources included financial, expertise and personnel.

Even when the expertise was present, it was recognised that TREs can be expensive, whether built in house or deployed by an external company and can be challenging to run. Some Trusts had staff in place for such work, and most were looking to expand their informatics and IT technical staff to increase digital capabilities. Most thought central funding should support this local activity.

Some larger NHS organisations (usually university associated Trusts) had cost models developed for data access and were in the process of developing their own TREs. Most Trusts felt enabling access to local data was necessary to drive health improvement for local or regional populations. Most felt that a local or regional approach was preferred compared to reliance on central provision, which was considered to be slow, expensive and less responsive to local/regional need. There was great interest in sharing models of data access between NHS Trusts, including blueprints for infrastructure, costs and governance, to enable organisations to create a sustainable offer.

9.3.2 Equity of Provision and Access

Resources and sustainability led to discussions around the growing maturity gap between digitally mature organisations, who had experience in servicing data access requests and either had, or were considering their own TREs, and the less digitally mature organisations. Both were represented at workshops.

The more digitally mature organisations spoke about the benefits they had seen from electronic health systems, and from research and quality improvements conducted using their own health data. Those without this capacity were engaged in activities to try and gain this capability.

All were concerned about the potential to create a two-tiered health system, where some could benefit from providing access to health data, and some could not. It was felt that central resources should support “levelling up”, enabling all hospitals to benefit from data sharing activities.

9.3.3 Public Trust

Public trust was felt fundamental to health data access and had to be protected and harnessed to support these emerging data tools. There was acknowledgement that the NHS is regarded as the most trustworthy actor with regard to health data, and it was essential to maintain this trust.

9.3.4 Harmonisation of Standards

There was recognition that TREs are in their infancy, and the terms “TRE” and “federated analytics” were used differently by different organisations. People were unsure which organisations should/would lead in standardising approaches.

There was clear support for harmonisation of the language, standards and frameworks governing the build and use of TREs and federated analytics for NHS organisations. Without agreed standards, many thought that TREs would be considered too risky by some organisations. The starting point for this work needed to be with the data owners, increasing understanding and confidence in the concept of data access and TREs.

There was felt to be little benefit from a tool developed in isolation in an academic setting or an external organisation, without NHS buy-in. Open standards and shared blueprints across NHS organisations were considered necessary.

9.3.5 Scale

There was some debate about the scale required for TREs and federated analytics. Some NHS organisations either had, or were actively developing their own TREs to house their own data for local/regional innovation. This was common in larger NHS organisations where organisations already felt they were benefiting from providing their own secure data access processes. Others suggested an Integrated Care System level to be the smallest unit which should be considered. None in attendance thought that central (national level) TREs should be the only offer. Reasons for this included a reduced ability to focus on regional health challenges, delays in central systems and data access, and a lack of data richness.

9.3.6 Interoperability

A key challenge across the data research landscape is the interoperability of any tools being used. There remained a limited ability to link health data (especially multi modal health data) captured using different systems across community and hospital care. While integrated care systems should resolve this, progress was variable across the country. There was even less ability to link health data

to other sources of data, and this was seen as being of increasing importance. However, there are examples of best practice which could be learned from.

9.4 Next Steps

Following the workshops, a report was published to capture the discussions above and was subsequently circulated to the attendees for any further feedback. It was agreed that the group would form a FED-NET working group to continue the conversation of how to support Trusts and bring together a network of experts and key decision-makers to provide guidance and share knowledge around TREs. This will help bring about greater equity of provision and access and the benefits of shared data.

The full report will be available on the **PIONEER** website.

Figure 5. Report produced and quotes from the FED-NET CCIO/CIO workshop

10. Work Package 6: Patient and Public Involvement

Aims

Patient and public involvement and engagement (PPIE) included reviews of data access throughout DTC, and a series of workshops discussed our approach to TREs and federation.

A central theme of FED-NET was to understand and then incorporate the views of the public and patients into our federated analytics programme. We sought to involve members of the public in the FED-NET programme to understand their views and support conversations about our planned programme of work, the benefits and challenges of federated analytics, and what this approach might mean for patients and their data.

In order to facilitate these conversations, the FED-NET programme held a series of workshops with members of the public, and representatives from the PIONEER Data Trust Committee (DTC) to co-design a brochure to explain federated analytics and the aims of FED-NET in an easy to understand way.

The workshops were attended by a diverse range of people, aged 16 – 84 in age and with 38% from BAME communities. The groups included varying degrees of health care utilisation, from very little to frequent tertiary care use due to complex health needs. The groups developed their own terms of references including payment schedules. For the youngest members we developed a young person's terms of reference and payment schedule, in agreement with their legal guardians.

The groups first agreed the broad headings of what should be included in a public brochure about federated analytics. Different public groups expanded these headings into outline text, working with field experts who advised on terminology and factual content. These were then shared around all the different groups to finalise the text. Next, graphical designers worked with public members to choose the style of brochure which might catch people's attention and help engage members of the public.

Once graphics were agreed, these were developed into a complete draft of the brochure. This was shared initially with all public members involved in the project for initial revision. The next version was trialled in various settings (community groups, hospital clinics) with feedback collated. The final version was completed with public members and approved by all partners. The finalised version can be found at <https://www.pioneerdatahub.co.uk/public-documents/what-is-federated-analytics-and-what-might-it-mean-for-me-and-my-health-data-a-guide-by-fed-net-and-pioneer/> and a series of stills are shown below (Section 10.1).

10.1 FED-NET Brochure

What is health data and how can it be used?

Health data is the information that doctors, nurses and other healthcare professionals collect about you when you visit a hospital, GP or other healthcare provider.

It includes what symptoms people have, the medical conditions they are diagnosed with, what investigations or treatments people receive, and how people respond to those treatments. This health data is used so that healthcare professionals can provide you with the best possible medical care.

Health data can also be used for research – to develop new treatments for patients, and to improve NHS services.

For health data research to improve healthcare for all patients, it needs to reflect us all - including people from different ethnicities, backgrounds, and with different health problems.

This brochure was written by members of the public and patients for members of the public and patients. It will explore how NHS health data can be used for research, how federated analytics can make health data use safer than ever, and what choices we have about how our health data is used.

Health data and its uses

Health data includes information not just about diseases, but about the kinds of people who suffer with a disease. This includes information about their age, whether they are male or female and sometimes their ethnicity or the jobs they do. It includes the other health problems they have, what medical tests or procedures people have undergone and what medications they use.

Health data is used to provide medical care. When health data is used for medical care, the data is identifiable. This means that the healthcare professional knows exactly whose health data it is, and uses the data to provide healthcare specifically for this person.

Health data can also be used for research. This can include discovering new ways of diagnosing or treating a disease, developing new devices for monitoring illnesses and identifying which patients would respond best to different treatments. When health data is used for research, it is de-identified, meaning that the researchers cannot tell who the data is about.

During research, de-identified health data from many, sometimes thousands of people, are placed together and analysed to look for patterns which tell researchers about diseases. When you combine lots of people's data, we call this a "data set".

Health data includes

What is federated analytics?

Federated analytics is a system where the data does not move, and instead the computer code the researchers write is sent to the data.

Sometimes the dataset is made from lots of pots of data in different settings. For example, a dataset studying asthma might include data from several hospitals around the country. Instead of the hospitals sending all that data to one TRE (as described on the previous page), in federated analytics each hospital would build their own TRE and keep their data within that TRE. In this situation, the researcher writes their computer code and this is then sent to each TRE, analysing only the data kept in that one TRE. The results from all the different TREs are then returned to the researchers and combined.

The figure below shows how this might happen.

Benefits of federated analytics

- The data providers (in this example, hospitals) always hold and control their own data. This is better for security.
- It is easier to identify which data has been used for which projects, and this can be done at a local level.

Challenges with federated analytics

- It is not as easy to check that the data has been collected in the same way. The data is not combined in one place, each data pot does not "see" the other data pots, and the researchers do not see the data at all, they just write and send code.
- It is unclear if analysing the data in "pots" and then combining the results alters how useful the results will be as this might make the results less accurate.
- The data providers (in this example, the hospital) have to build and run their own TRE

What are the advantages and disadvantages of federated analytics?

Advantages

- The local organisation keeps full control of the data and only has to allow access to its own data
- The data stays put and is not sent anywhere. Computer code to perform the research is sent to the data
- The local organisation has control over who accesses the data
- The local organisation can audit and check which data is used for which project

Disadvantages

- As each organisation only "sees" its own data, it is harder to check that the data has been collected in the same way
- It is harder to know what the whole dataset looks like, as data is spread across organisations
- The researcher does not see the data, and cannot check if the dataset has everything they need for the research project
- It is unknown whether analysing data in "pots" and combing the results loses any meaning or accuracy
- The local organisation has to know how to build and run a TRE

10.2 FED-NET Dissemination Workshop

The final FED-NET patient and public workshop was held virtually on the 28th July 2022. Following brief presentations on what federated analytics is and what it might mean for the NHS and patients, there was an open discussion between our attendees about FED-NET.

The attendees were from across the UK from diverse backgrounds, ranging in age from 19 to 75 and all with varying experience in discussing health data and health care research. This document is a summary of the discussions from the workshop and the feedback on the FED-NET brochure.

10.2.1 FED-NET Feedback

Several themes emerged through the course of the group discussion. These were NHS resources; equity of provision and access; public trust; data security; the scope of available data and data accuracy.

10.2.2 NHS Resources

There was agreement that the use of health data is key to providing better care to patients. Attendees highlighted that finding the required resources – time, money and expertise - to develop and deploy Trusted Research Environments (TREs) in the NHS was a challenge for NHS organisations.

“Does the NHS have the resources to do this at the moment?”

At a time of constrained NHS budgets and staff shortages, some NHS Trusts may not have the capacity or resource to complete this type of work.

It was agreed that investment is needed in NHS IT infrastructure to support this type of work.

Initiatives like the HDR UK Data Hubs, such as PIONEER, were felt to be important, as they can work with other NHS organisations to help them make their data accessible in a safe and secure manner.

“Data is the way forward...Eventually, all hospitals will need to develop this expertise.”

10.2.3 Public Trust

Like with many discussions around sharing of sensitive health data, the theme of public trust was explored and how federated analytics could increase public trust. However, there was concern over who would control the data and how the national data opt-out would work on federated data. The FED-NET team emphasised the national data opt-out would still apply to federated data and the data would remain under the control and ownership of the healthcare organisation, for example, the NHS Trust. The group

“Data has such a bad name!”

emphasised that the NHS, and especially regional healthcare organisations, were the most trusted when storing health data.

“I would be worried if data was controlled by private bodies. This will cause a phenomenal amount of fear for some communities.”

The public group recognised the potential of data to transform patient care in the NHS. They emphasised the importance of clearly communicating the value of making health data accessible during discussions with the public and explaining the different ways data is collected, managed⁴ and protected.

The key to building trust is to promote ‘good news’ stories about data. There are clear examples of where access to data has improved health care and outcomes for people. Complicated projects using less well understood techniques such as Artificial Intelligence⁵ (AI) are often misunderstood and attract negative press, especially when things go wrong. It may be beneficial to start with smaller, less-complex projects to build trust with the public first.

“Communication with public and patients about how data use is beneficial needs to start from a really basic level.”

10.2.4 Access and Compatibility

A major concern of all workshop attendees was ensuring that everyone had the opportunity to benefit from health data research. It was recognised that the resource-challenge to make health data accessible in a secure and timely manner would be felt differently across different healthcare settings. This already means that some NHS healthcare providers are being left behind; to the disadvantage of the patient populations they serve.

“There is the potential for exclusion of large groups of patients, which includes hard to reach groups and areas of deprivation.”

“You need to be sure that you are not collecting data solely from places that are able to work with this system.”

The group also discussed the disparity between digitally-mature Trusts and less digitally-mature Trusts, and how this could increase health inequalities.

NHS care organisations used different types and makes of electronic health systems. It was felt to be impractical for every NHS organisation to have to use the same system to take part in federated analytics. Combining data analysis from different care settings and organisations required systems that could work across different care settings and different electronic systems. One of the important factors FED-NET wanted to address is ensuring that the system could use many different forms of data and could be ‘interoperable’ or work across different electronic health systems

“I worry about the exclusion of some smaller community hospitals who still use paper records. This means data from a large rural population wouldn’t be included.”

⁴ You can choose to stop your patient information being used for research for plan Data Opt Out, and applies to anyone over the age of 13 living in England. You can read more here: <https://www.nhs.uk/your-nhs-data-matters/>

⁵ Artificial intelligence can be defined as a cross-disciplinary approach to understanding, modelling, and replicating intelligence and cognitive processes invoking various computational, mathematical, logical, mechanical, and even biological principles and devices.

– so no organisation is left out because they may use a different system. The public workshop attendees strongly endorsed this “open standards” approach – where systems developed could work across different electronic health record providers to minimise any issues of compatibility.

10.2.5 Data Security, Availability and Accuracy

There was discussion around the security, accuracy and availability of data when using federated analytics. One of the noted benefits of federated analytics is that the data does not leave the local organisation, and the local organisation has much greater control over who can access the data.

“Researchers don’t know what data there is, so how will they know what question to ask.”

There were also concerns that as the researchers do not see the data when using federated analytics, then they will not know if the requested data set has all the information they need for their project. Data Hubs, like PIONEER, should support researchers with identifying what data they need and ensuring that data is ‘research ready’.

“Is there a risk of missing data making analysis impossible?”

A specific challenge of federated analytics is that it is unknown whether combining different results will mean a loss of accuracy in the data overall. While there are a lot of initiatives at local organisations to improve data accuracy, this often remains a challenge of using health

data, but for patient care and for research. The workshop attendees recommended that more research is needed to test the accuracy of federated versus pooled data analysis for different types of research questions, to better understand how accurate this approach could be. There may be times when federated analytics are adequate to answer a question, and times when only pooled data can be used. Public trust will be enhanced by making sure the right approach is chosen for question being asked.

“So many patients have encountered issues with data being inaccurate that they rightly worry about it being used for important things.”

The group discussed that there is a challenge when handling data relating to a small group of patients, such as people with a rare disease. Here, there were concerns that analysing a small number of patients from a specific location might make re-identification easier, whereas pooling data from across care settings might protect identity better. In these cases, a federated approach may not be the best option, unless geography could be masked. In these cases, asking the patients directly whether they are happy for their data to be used would be the best option, or working with representative patient groups.

“Is there a risk that a patient with a rare disease at a small hospital would be identifiable if the population size was small?”

In summary, the public group voiced their support but also concerns about federated analytics, and specifically wanted more research as to the accuracy of results and reassurances that regional centres and their patients would all benefit these technological advances. For a copy of the full report, see the PIONEER website.

11. Impacts

We are pleased to have met all our deliverables and can report the following impacts:

- Built blueprints and code templates for federated TRE networks.
- Produced a deeply phenotyped cross-council research asset covering two large acute trusts and BRCs. This data asset includes electronic health records data, experimental biomarker data, meteorological and air quality data.
- Built a synthetic data asset from this complex real-world data
- Mapped the limitations of common data models (OMOP) versus native language for our diverse data assets.
- Increased our understanding of more readily extensible data models than the current CDMs in widespread use.
- Enabled traditional statistical methodologies to be federated across two TREs without direct exposure of sensitive data to researchers or transferring data between data controllers.
- Expanded of a publicly co-produced information governance framework.
- Increased public awareness of TREs and federated analytics and co-developed a resource to continue engaging with the public

FED-NET is a **technology demonstrator**, built on existing, secure infrastructure (PIONEER Hub) with a providence of servicing multiple, multi-model data requests. It offers a framework for **best practice for information governance** (IG), co-developed with lay members, which has increased trust in data secondary use. Our solution will form a scalable blueprint for cross-council collaborations, vital to tackling the complex challenges faced by our global population.

Beneficiaries include data subjects, the public, academic, NHS, commercial, policy and third sector researchers, all of whom have co-developed our approach.

The use case includes meteorological, experimental medicine trial data, health and laboratory data with cutting edge data science, of interest to commercial and academic communities. Cross-council remit includes NERC, EPSRC, MRC and InnovateUK.

FED-NET has tested the deployment of federated analytics, mapping data of different ontologies into a common model, and a shared governance model, including the potential for financial sustainability. The impacts include:

- The expansion of a TRE blueprint, meeting NHSX requirements, which NHS Data Controllers have shown confidence in.
- A blueprint for federated analytics, shaped by Data controller & end user experience/feedback.

- A gap analysis of common data models when applied to the chosen use case (meteorological and pollution data, laboratory cytokine data and routinely collected health data (co-morbidities, physiology, pathology, prescribing) in an asthma cohort.
- An increase in data assets for cross-sector council work, discoverable on HDR UK's Innovation Gateway.
- The expansion of a publicly co-produced information governance framework across a further NHS Trust, to test the scalability of our approach, built to the "5 safes" framework.
- Public involvement and engagement with TRE build and use.
- An open access publication, written with DARE UK to share learning.

Subsequent phases will include:

- Expanding the federated analytics footprint
- Filling common data model language "gaps"
- Adding to data modalities
- Exploring "TRE build & run" as a business model.
- Expand and optimise the application scenarios and optimisation techniques.

12. Conclusion

FED-NET tested whether federated analytics could offer a scalable solution to the technical and governance challenges of analysing datasets separated by geography and data language.

We curated a real-world dataset including electronic health record, meteorological, air quality and inflammatory biomarker data for patients with asthma. We built a synthetic dataset of the same parameters and have been able to demonstrate, for this data, which of the four tabular models in the SDV library, although both TVAE (constrained) and CT-GAN (constrained) both produced outputs closely resembling the template data, CT-GAN was selected as TVAE was sensitive to unbalanced counts. Our tests to examine if standardised data models/languages were useful with such a complex dataset supported our initial hypothesis that the decision of whether (and which) common data model (CDM) to apply should be driven by the research requirements. The data transformation to OMOP is time consuming using considerable resource, beyond what would be required for our normal raw data extractions. Once mapped the benefits to allow large scale distribution and federated analyses is clear, however it is worth noting that for the FED-NET cross-council dataset only 51.2% of fields directly transformed into OMOP.

We developed and tested a federated analytical environment via the three work packages focussing on technical architecture, data infrastructure and federated analytics. FED-NET benefitted greatly from PIONEER's cutting-edge fully developed TRE infrastructure, as the team were able to focus on developing the core for federation including the ability to push information and interfaces to share metadata and analytics. We performed federated analytics across multiple TREs, testing the accuracy of results when using different federated approaches versus pooling the data. Work package 1 (Technical Architecture) enabled us to build and test the technical architecture to perform federated analytics between TREs with the same and different underpinning structures. The FED-NET team within PIONEER team were able to spin up 5 differing blueprint TREs for federated testing. Furthermore, the team were able to test federating with an on-premise solution. We felt this was an important finding, as some NHS trusts or organisations may not have the time or resource to spin up TREs, so this method would enable them to participate in projects.

We worked with healthcare organisations from across the UK to understand their requirements for federated analytics. This was co-developed into a report and a working group has been formed for future discussions. The report highlights the interest NHS organisations have in making their data discoverable, but the concerns they have about who is leading on a standardised framework, being required to use the same EHS and being directed into a national approach which impedes regional innovation. These concerns should be explored further.

We worked with diverse patients and members of the public to understand what they wanted to know about federated analytics. We co-produced a public brochure to explain federated analytics. This is now being trialled in wider public groups. In workshops, there was considerable support for federated analytics, but only if accuracy of findings could be proven, and that less digitally mature trusts (and the patients they serve) benefit from this innovation.

Throughout this sprint FED-NET has sought to align with the DARE UK aims to design and deliver a national data research infrastructure that demonstrates trustworthiness and supports research at scale for public good. We believe this sprint project has contributed to the national design standard by testing how we can simplify the healthcare data landscapes so the warehouses (research analytics) and lakes (clinical operational use) become interchangeable.

In summary by federating access to two trust's sensitive health data alongside other cross-council data, using innovative architecture and industry software, FED-NET has increased the availability of rich longitudinal data, linked to environmental data.

By building a system which can apply common data models, where applicable, to diverse combined datasets for federated analysis, we have increased the opportunities for cross-council research. We believe there are challenges to federated analytics but the opportunities this brings for data where there are privacy and confidentiality concerns are considerable and we are keen to continue to pursue our work around this.

Through public involvement/engagement and applying governance processes co-developed with the public, we have continued to increase transparency and public trust in data research.

The next phase of development should focus on federation across different TRE architectures, finding solutions for less digitally mature Trusts and testing the accuracy of federated analytics across different use cases.

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